

BRA const	00111101xx001001000
BRA misc const	00xxxxx1xx001001000
BRA lit	00111100xx0001001000
BRA misc lit	00xxxxx0xx0001001000
BRX misc reg lit	00xxxxx0xx0101001000
BRX reg lit	00111100xx0101001000
BRX const	00111101xx101001000
BRX misc const	00xxxxx1xx101001000
PCNT const	00xxxxx1xx110101000
PCNT lit	00xxxxx0xx0110101000
CONT misc	00xx0101011000
CONT	0011110xx0101011000
PBK lit	00xxxxx0xx0010101000
PBK const	00xxxxx1xx010101000
BRK misc	00xx0001011000
BRK	0011110xx0001011000
CAL const	00xxxxx1xx011001000
CAL lit	00xxxxx0xx0011001000
RET misc	00xx0010011000
RET	0011110xx0010011000
EXIT misc	00xx0000011000
EXIT	0011110xx0000011000
NOP misc lit	01xx0110100001
NOP lit	01xxxxxxxx11110xx0110100001
BPT lit	00xx0000000000
S2R reg sreg	01xx1001100001
PSETP p p p p p	01xx0100100001
PSET reg p p p	01xx1000100001
FLO reg reg	01xx0110000111
FLO reg const	01xx0110000110
P2R reg misc reg lit	10xx1001100011
P2R reg misc reg const	01xx1001100110
R2P misc reg lit	10xx000101100011
R2P misc reg const	01xx100101100110
TEX reg reg lit tex lit	10xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx1111111xx110
TEX reg reg reg lit tex lit	xx110
TEXDEPBAR lit	01xx0011101110
RRO reg reg	01xx0100100111
RRO reg const	01xx0100100110
PRMT reg reg lit reg	10xx0001101101
DMNMX reg reg reg p	01xx0101000111
DMNMX reg reg const p	01xx0101000110
FMNMX reg reg lit p	10xx0011000011
FMNMX reg reg reg p	01xx0011000111
FMNMX reg reg const p	01xx0011000110
VOTE p p	011111111xx1101100001
VOTE reg p p	01xx1101100001
POPC reg reg reg	01xx1000000111
POPC reg reg const	01xx1000000110
MEMBAR	01xx1100111110
CSETP p p misc p	01xx0010100001
ISCADD32I reg reg lit lit	00xx0xxxxx101
TLD reg reg lit tex lit	01xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx1111111xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx1110
TLD reg reg reg lit tex lit	01xx1110

